

PATHWAYS TO JUST LANDSCAPE TRANSFORMATION

barriers, opportunities, recommendations

A STRATEGY PAPER BASED ON COOPERATION WITH WORKSHOP PARTICIPANTS IN THE SLOVÁCKO, VALAŠKO AND HORŇÁCKO REGIONS

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SUMMARY

The Just Scapes project was officially launched in 2020. The consortium of three countries (the UK, France and the Czech Republic) has been doing research in three types of landscape: the Scottish Highlands, the French rural landscape of the south-eastern Pyrénées and the Czech cultural landscape of southern and eastern Moravia. Just Scapes focuses primarily on the mechanisms and processes of just transformation, and the following questions, the answers to which are crucial for the future: How are the impacts of climate change distributed? How are the impacts and effects of landscape management and climate change policies distributed?

Our research was based on the „Just Transformation Labs“ approach (T-labs). This approach is specifically tailored to support collaborative solutions to complex social problems. Included in our research were also extensive field visits and cooperation with relevant key stakeholders. We also conducted numerous interviews and workshops.

KEY LANDSCAPE TRANSFORMATION TOPICS

Active citizenship: *Involvement in what is happening (in the community, in the environment, in the company); motivation or determination to do things differently (better).*

Keeping promises, respecting agreements

Complying with laws and rules, *respecting legislation*

Fairness

Seeking consensus, *respecting all parties involved, seeking compromise*

Communication *with focus on the meaning and the intent of measures and changes*

Morality *of action*

Responsibility *for entrusted resources (land, forest, water, communal land, range).*

Consideration *for one another and for the landscape*

Willingness *to help*

Respect *for nature, natural resources, people*

Associating with each other, *re-establishing clubs/societies/associations, jointly organising rural renewal*

Decency and politeness in (dis)agreements

Working together *to preserve and improve living conditions, and to defend common and public interests*

Setting and promoting *common goals, building community*

Care

Helpfulness, *lack of spite*

Interest *in the environment, new possibilities, changes, innovations*

Interest in **educating oneself**

Responsibility *for us all and the future of the planet*

INTRODUCTION

This text is a result of a long-term research collaboration with key actors who manage the landscape in five wine-growing and agricultural areas of southern and eastern Moravia. Our focus was on **the mechanisms of just transformation**. If the current state of the landscape leads to its vulnerability to climate change impacts, we must ask what **changes need to be made to increase its resilience; this is exactly what the project has succeeded in defining**.

Agricultural landscape can be viewed as a space in which the influence of farming intersects with the influence of state administration, legislation and local community life.

The landscape of southern and eastern Moravia has a long winegrowing and farming history, but the quality of the local soil and its capacity to retain water has been marked by intensive farming practices. The character of the landscape, defined by **vast swathes of fields, further weakens its ability to cope with climate change impacts. This requires a change in approach**.

If we want to picture a landscape that is to be resilient to climate change impacts in the future and should, in this respect, undergo transformation towards sustainability, it is essential that we take into account the perspective of the local people, to whom it is intrinsically linked and by whom it is managed and governed. They cannot be left out.

Just transformation is to be understood as a situation in which the landscape undergoes the desired changes towards recovery. These changes have to be based **on the perspective of those who live there**: local government, farmers and residents. Only then will they ultimately benefit both human society and other living beings in the landscape.

To acquire key input and answers to the questions mentioned at the beginning of the text, we spent almost three years with our key landscape management actors. Together we named the barriers and opportunities associated with the necessary changes, and we recorded the actors' perspective and proposed solutions. **The purpose of this paper** is to provide relevant policymakers with a set of recommendations based on our long-term stay in the field, and the interviews and workshops where we asked the actors a simple question: **What needs to be done to achieve the required changes?**

RESEARCH CONTEXT

Project Just Scapes and just transformation in practice: increasing landscape resilience to climate change impacts and engaging local communities in transformation processes across three European case studies.

Just transformation in the context of the Czech case study

Each of the three case studies is intrinsically linked to the systemic and legislative dimensions of landscape management. **In the Czech context**, the agricultural landscape is marked by the 1947 **land reform** (nationalisation of private land) and the **subsequent intensive farmland management**. This historical context has caused significant problems in local attitudes to land ownership and the loss of attachment to land; unfortunately, the negative impact continues even today. **It is currently complicating the efforts to transition to sustainable farming practices and to implement adaptation measures.**

The systemic dimension of the Czech case study is further defined by **legislative barriers in land management and by the way agricultural subsidies are allocated**. The key actors we interviewed often perceived **the state as one of the barriers** that small-scale farming businesses face. They view the state's legislative and economic actions as the continuation of the socialist tradition, where the goal is to use the land for maximum profit, rather than to create support for a diverse, biodiversity-rich landscape.

The current situation in Czech agriculture is often perceived as supporting the production of degraded landscapes, where everything comes second to profit, and land is exploited to its limits. In addition, **the subsidy system has been described as favouring large agricultural players**. Reflecting this, our research focused not only **on the relationship between people's willingness to accept and implement transformative changes in the landscape** that surrounds them, but also on **their perception of the legislative and physical context of these changes**. Our primary focus was changes related to climate change adaptations. **Together with the participants, we named the barriers that prevent the adoption of more sustainable strategies in landscape management**. We were particularly interested in the attitudes of farmers and landowners towards sustainable farming (technologies, strategies, etc.) and its viability in the long-term.

We also **focused on the motivation and context** that underpin how farmers, landowners and representatives of the local government adopt specific land management practices. At the same time, **we paid attention to their perceptions of just and acceptable forms of future sustainable strategies within agribusiness, particularly in the areas of agricultural and development policies and subsidies.**

CONDITIONS FOR JUST TRANSFORMATION: PEOPLE, LIFE IN THE LANDSCAPE AND NATURE

We devote the following pages of this document to **specific recommendations for overcoming barriers to just landscape transformation**, but we would like to briefly highlight the **deeper conditions for just transformation** first. Together with our participants, we decided **to explore the social and narrative nature of the changes that cultural landscapes**, and the communities inherently linked to them, **need for continued survival**. We attempted to define what lies at the root of these changes in terms of the thoughts, emotions, stories and motivations that shape the way people think about and approach landscape transformations. **We were able to define several areas that our participants considered crucial for just landscape transformation.**

At the level of the individual, the participants viewed humility and concern for the context of “healthy landscape” as important.

The basic building block of the participants’ reflections on transformative processes was awareness **of the responsibility for one’s own life**; the moment someone acknowledges responsibility for their life decisions, they also take responsibility for the external, physical and social world, which we all are part of. The most immediate dimension of this world, then, is the landscape in which the existence of individuals and communities manifests. This “landscape of the home”, and in particular its vulnerable state, were seen as the mirror of a lifestyle focused on profit and the commodification of the environment. Such an approach also implies a disconnection from the real state of the landscape, a loss of attachment to it and a certain ignorance of (or disinterest in) the context of its condition. **In order to achieve a just transformation**, we have to approach the landscape **responsibly and with respect for its real needs**. Our participants’ narratives did not describe this as giving up all comforts and denying the needs of human communities, which are undeniably part of the cultural landscape; **it was rather about striking a balance between the need for a comfortable life and the respect for and understanding of the realities of life in the rural landscape**. This shift in thinking then defined the participants’ reflections on lifestyle. How do we change it and orient it more towards the needs of the landscape as a whole, rather than individual needs?

At the level of community, responsibility beyond the individual was considered essential by our participants. This responsibility operates with a more communal mindset where we all collectively answer for the state of the landscape and its future direction.

Communities are **powerful social structures** that go beyond the level of individuals in their ability to make decisions and **achieve change through consensus and mutual sharing**. In the participants’ subjective perceptions, the collective power of communities was associated with significant transformative potential. **They saw its power in the possible cooperation of individual actors, and the co-creation of a healthy physical and social landscape**. A frequently invoked theme was the **process of building food security**, where the different parts of production, supply and consumption chains work together to co-create responsible local supply and demand, thereby ensuring the security

of the future landscape and of the present and future generations. The same meaning lies within the idea of “**active citizenship**”, i.e. **people’s responsibility not only for their individual existence within the community and the landscape, but also for actions that can damage them**. Active citizenship also includes working with information and concern for the context of the processes that take place in the immediate environment of the communities. The active dimension also represents the idea that actors participate in these processes, and they co-construct and co-direct them. Finally, **rural communities were seen as the custodians of traditions and old ties to the landscape and its processes**. In order to achieve a just transformation - one that is conscious and aware of the local landscape and social processes - transformative processes need to be grounded precisely in this deep knowledge of the landscape and its needs, based on traditions and ties to home.

Society-level conditions for transformative processes connect the individual-level and community-level interests that transcend the geographical space of local landscapes.

One of the conditions transcending the individual and community level of landscape transformation processes included in the participants’ narratives was **social responsibility for and universal access to a shared landscape**. At this level, the notion of the “**active citizen**” extends to “**active inhabitant**”, and it comes from the assumption that local landscapes merge into a mosaic of a shared world, and each local landscape must be approached responsibly and sensitively for this mosaic to be appropriately cared for and managed. A just landscape transformation rooted in social responsibility is therefore a process of conscious landscape management in the spirit of the idea that all local processes are interconnected and interdependent with other geographical and social spaces. What are the basic building blocks of such an approach then? Sensitivity to the needs of landscapes and the communities living in them, knowledge of the local context, and the motivation to contribute to positive change within social and geographically defined worlds.

Lastly, we and the participants engaged with conditions for just transformation at the level of legislators and policy makers.

Another area in need of transformation was **legislation**. The alpha and omega of this transformation is the openness of legislators to systemic changes based on the voices and suggestions of the people who manage landscapes, and the ordinary people. This openness brings forth a willingness to listen and respond flexibly. **Positive development is also contingent on the state’s adoption of a partnership approach, and the transformation of the state’s role towards a participative direction, where it formulates measures and laws together with all stakeholders.**

Just transformation is first and foremost about the openness of all stakeholders to changing established frameworks of thought: herein lay the great uncertainty and fear on the part of all our participants. In addition to just transformation, stability and the preservation of what the participants perceived as functional and safe in terms of their familiar social and physical space were also essential. Respect for the needs and the pace of individuals and communities is therefore also a completely valid condition for a just transformation to occur, for it is they who will ultimately shoulder any transformative processes and results of these changes.

RESEARCH DESIGN AND METHODS OF DATA COLLECTION

An illustration of a landscape with a path leading through various elements. On the left, there are stylized buildings in yellow and blue, and a green tree. A large orange arrow points from left to right across the middle. Below the arrow is a dark red area with green grass-like shapes and a white cloud-like shape with purple stems. At the bottom left is a red building. A blue speech bubble is at the top right, and a green speech bubble is at the bottom right. A small blue note is on the left side of the path.

Our research was based on the transdisciplinary “Just Transformation Labs” (T-labs) approach, which is specifically tailored to encourage the collaboration of diverse groups of actors in solving complex societal problems.

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We conducted forty semi-structured interviews with key stakeholders (including policymakers) and ten participatory workshops which were attended by over eighty people in total.

KEY STAKEHOLDERS (PARTICIPANTS)

In order to understand the context of agricultural policies and their links to the actual practice in agricultural landscapes, we worked with the following types of social actors:

KEY TOPICS

The following section presents the key topics that emerged from our semi-structured and informal interviews, expert consultations and participatory workshops that we conducted with key stakeholders over the past three years. These are the topics that cover a number of barriers that our stakeholders considered crucial when it comes to landscape transformation.

How these topics interconnect is visualised by the diagram on page 9. The most problematic of these, in the view of the key actors involved in our research, was the inappropriately designed legislative and bureaucratic system - specifically the confusing policies, the frequent changes and the problematic dealings with officials (especially in relation to LPIS). **The primary theme linking the above points was the loss of trust in the system and the scepticism towards the current system of policies.**

Another important group of topics revolved around land ownership. These topics, and the barriers associated with them, concerned the issue of leases and landscape management, and related policies that make landscape management (not) possible. This group of topics also included barriers reflecting different agricultural and management practices, and their (un)sustainability.

The last large group of topics consisted of those related to planting greenery in the landscape, increasing landscape permeability and with other physical, transformative, landscape features, all with the aim of increasing landscape resilience to climate change impacts.

The following pages include these most important topics (i.e. most frequently addressed by all key stakeholder groups). **Above all, there are also recommendations** proposed and compiled by the stakeholders for each topic, and they are linked to the relevant government institutions; it is government institutions that these recommendations are primarily addressed to.

RECOMMENDATIONS GROUPED BY KEY TOPIC

LEGISLATION

In our research, the term “legislation” refers to the set of all laws, regulations and directives related to land and landscape management. Nevertheless, we primarily focused on where our key stakeholders saw barriers in the legislative processes and legislative instruments when it comes to landscape management; what hinders or prevents transformations towards greater resilience and sustainability. The most salient topics concerning legislation for the actors involved were as follows: some laws lack clarity, rules change every year and, this especially, some legislative acts are far too complex and intricate considering how crucial they are to the people who manage land. Digitisation of legislative processes was mentioned as a problem primarily in relation to older citizens, for whom there is no adequate information and support system.

LEGISLATION: BUREAUCRACY

COMPLEX LAND CONSOLIDATION

Complex land consolidation is a key tool for change in the landscape. The varied interests and motivations of different people and groups may clash during implementation; this is logical. Land consolidation can, nevertheless, facilitate changes towards more sustainable ways of land management: by helping to clarify ownership relationships; by enabling people (private individuals as well as municipalities) to have more control over what happens to their land. We are talking about farming practices, building, or adapting to changes in the landscape. Unfinished land consolidation hinders landscape transformations and makes it difficult to implement sustainable management measures.

SUBSIDIES

The primary problem with the current design of the subsidy system, in the narratives of our key actors, was that it tends to support unsustainable practices and does not sufficiently reflect the real needs of the landscape or the people who manage it. The other most frequently mentioned barriers were: (1) acreage-based subsidies favour large-scale farmers - the vast fields they cultivate allow them to receive higher sums, further encouraging unsustainable farming practices; (2) subsidies are often very confusing - the conditions change every year, which makes it difficult to apply for them; (3) lack of knowledge on the part of the LPIS staff, who leave out green areas in farmers' fields and then provide smaller funding. There has been a regulation in force since 2014 which stipulates that if growth under trees is cut or grazed on, this course of action is not allowed - on the contrary, it allows for additional support for the maintenance of this growth.

LAND OWNERSHIP AND LEASE

Land ownership plays a key role in landscape transformations. It is the owners who decide what happens to their land, who manages it and how (or to whom they lease or sell it). At the same time, they are often out of contact with their land, and with the soil (its quality, condition, etc.), as well as with those who use or manage it.

The owners' lack of contact with their land makes long-term land leases (for more than ten years) even more difficult to reach.

There are several actors who have influence on land management. The owner is the one who owns the land (whether it is a private individual, a legal entity or a municipality). However, owners rarely manage their land themselves. The land is rented to farmers (or agricultural cooperatives) who manage it under an usufructuary lease. They are the ones who effectively shape it and are responsible for its quality and condition. On the other hand, they can also degrade it through inappropriate practices. The negative consequences of renting include: (1) Possible (and often irreversible) soil degradation. It primarily occurs as a result of intensive farming practices (inappropriate crop mix, overuse of chemicals, overly large monoculture farming blocks). The soil is then gradually depleted (decreased soil fertility), which ultimately leads farmers to use additional chemicals again in order to be able to harvest crops. Gradual soil degradation then makes the soil decrease in value. (2) Soil is run off into municipalities during flash floods, causing irreversible loss of topsoil.

FARMING PRACTICES

The topic of farming practices groups together specific weaknesses associated with intensive farming in the landscape, and specific ways of managing land. Both reduce the landscape's resilience to climate change impacts and leave it damaged and vulnerable. At the same time, intensive farming, the selection of monoculture crops and an overall profit-over-health approach to landscape management gradually reduce soil quality. This approach ultimately puts local communities at existential risk.

GREEN FEATURES IN THE LANDSCAPE

Implementation of green features in the landscape was a burning issue, especially for participants from the agricultural sector. The narratives of our key actors defined the primary problem in successful implementation as the lack of systemic (state) support in the areas of legislation, information and capacity. Another contributor is a combination of owner disinterest (or lack of knowledge and awareness of the quality and condition of their land) and the aforementioned intensive farming practices. These not only lead to soil degradation, they also create barriers to implementation of bio-corridors, green features and adaptation measures in the landscape.

FOOD SOVEREIGNTY

Our actors identified food sovereignty as a key aspect of future survival. Without local food and without the support of local supply chains, local farming communities cannot continue to exist in the landscape.

EDUCATION AND AWARENESS I

Our participants felt it was important to educate the public to give them a better understanding of relationships in the landscape, the landscape's attributes and needs. In a broader sense it meant awareness-raising, specifically the scope and reach of public (and other) media. More narrowly they spoke about the domain of schools, where they saw high educational potential. The key actors considered the municipality and the community to have a similar role to schools, their best tools being the radio and the municipal newsletter. Awareness-raising was viewed as a powerful (although frequently underutilised) tool for landscape transformations due to its wide reach and educational potential.

EDUCATION AND AWARENESS II

MORE

**RECOMMENDATIONS
GROUPED
BY TARGET
ACTOR**

EU

- Implementing the same rules for agricultural and economic activity and landscape management across countries.
- Supporting people's responsibility for land and the landscape.

GOVERNMENT OF THE CZECH REPUBLIC

- Redesigning legislation so that it is no longer a barrier for farmers (making certain regulations comprehensive to prevent regulations from changing every year).
- Stabilising laws and repealing unnecessary ones. Making sure laws allow for situations where farmers inadvertently make a mistake, meeting them halfway.
- Making legislation clear; eliminating or at least reducing administrative burdens for farmers.
- Increasing corporate social responsibility.
- Introducing minimum purchase prices for food and products.
- Supporting people's responsibility for land and the landscape.
- Supporting municipal leadership - financially and by providing information and capacities - to lease municipal land to responsible farmers.
- Making it possible for municipalities to buy more land.
- Improve and promote communication between authorities.

MINISTRY OF THE ENVIRONMENT

- Supporting the training of officials towards better familiarity with agricultural regulations and their regular amendments.
- Making legislation clear; eliminating or at least reducing administrative burdens for farmers. Stabilising laws and repealing unnecessary ones. Making sure laws allow for situations where farmers inadvertently make a mistake, meeting them halfway.
- Redesigning legislation so that it is no longer a barrier for farmers (making regulations comprehensive to prevent regulations from changing every year).
- Establishing the position of farming consultant in the respective offices.
- Ensuring increased support for local farmers' products (supply chains support) with respect to capacities of the "what to sell" nature (cultivation support) and the "where and by whom" nature (supplying space for markets and buyers).
- Ensuring increased subsidy and systemic (legislative and bureaucratic) support for local supply chains.
- Providing financial support to municipalities for landscape revitalisation; making municipalities responsible for landscape care.
- Establishing the position of municipal land management consultant.
- Giving more power to farmers: they know their land best, and a third party should not be making decisions for them.
- Producing educational and awareness workshops for landowners.
- Increasing government subsidy (and human resource) support to municipalities when it comes to sustainability and awareness-raising measures.
- Developing a budget based on communication and participation with targeted beneficiaries.
- Removing barriers associated with subsidies: making subsidies clearer, integrating them and allocating them to meaningful and responsible activities. Making subsidies flexible according to the actual needs of the farmer and the condition of the landscape.
- Redesigning subsidies to encourage the creation of healthy landscapes instead of growing crops primarily for profit.
- When providing subsidies, take into account the needs of different types of farms according to size and focus (e.g. vegetable farm).
- Removing barriers associated with subsidies: making subsidies clearer, integrating them and allocating them to meaningful and responsible activities. Making subsidies flexible according to the actual needs of the farmer and the condition of the landscape.
- Incorporating into legislation the lived experience of the people who manage land, local government representatives and local residents.
- Improving and promoting communication amongst authorities.

MINISTRY OF REGIONAL DEVELOPMENT

- Increase government subsidy (and human-capacity) support to municipalities in relation to sustainability and outreach measures.
- Developing a budget based on communication and participation with targeted beneficiaries.
- Removing barriers associated with subsidies: making subsidies clearer, integrating them and allocating them to meaningful and responsible activities. Making subsidies flexible according to the actual needs of the farmer and the condition of the landscape.
- Redesigning legislation so that it is no longer a barrier for farmers (making regulations comprehensive to prevent regulations from changing every year).
- Incorporating into legislation the lived experience of the people who manage land, local government representatives and local residents.
- Establishing the position of farming consultant in the respective offices.
- Improving and promoting communication amongst authorities.
- Taking public benefit more strongly into account when awarding subsidies.
- Making it mandatory for municipalities to care for the landscape - allocating subsidies based on their activities.
- Remove the barriers associated with subsidies: make them transparent, unify them, allocate them to meaningful and responsible activities, make them flexible according to the real needs of the farmer and the state of the landscape.
- Developing a budget based on communication and participation with targeted beneficiaries
- Giving more power to farmers: they know their land best, and a third party should not be making decisions for them.
- Establishing the position of municipal land management consultant.
- Providing financial support to municipalities for landscape revitalisation; making municipalities responsible for landscape care.
- Ensuring increased subsidy and systemic (legislative and bureaucratic) support for local supply chains.
- Ensuring increased support for local farmers' products (supply chains support) with respect to capacities of the "what to sell" nature (cultivation support) and the "where and by whom" nature (supplying space for markets and buyers).
- Launching information campaigns (let the public know about the farmers and their products).

MINISTRY OF AGRICULTURE

- Supporting the training of officials towards better familiarity with agricultural regulations and their regular amendments.
- Creating a department for soil formation with trained experts.
- Establishing the position of farming consultant in the respective offices.
- Making legislation clear; eliminating or at least reducing administrative burdens for farmers.
- Redesigning legislation so that it is no longer a barrier for farmers (making certain regulations comprehensive to prevent regulations from changing every year).
- Launching information campaigns (let the public know about the farmers and their products).
- Ensuring increased support for local farmers' products (supply chains support) with respect to capacities of the "what to sell" nature (cultivation support) and the "where and by whom" nature (supplying space for markets and buyers).
- Ensuring increased subsidy and systemic (legislative and bureaucratic) support for local supply chains.
- Establishing the position of municipal land management consultant.
- Giving more power to farmers: they know their land best, and a third party should not be making decisions for them.
- Supporting people's responsibility for land and landscape.
- Producing educational and awareness workshops for landowners.
- When providing subsidies, taking into account the needs of different types of farms according to size and focus (e.g. vegetable farms, dairy farms, etc.).
- Redrafting subsidies to encourage the production of healthy landscapes as opposed to the growing of crops primarily for profit.
- Supporting blocks of land of no more than 10 Ha and taking into account the higher costs associated with transitioning into cultivation of smaller blocks of land.
- Using subsidies to control and regulate the activities of large companies.
- Increasing government subsidy (and human resource) support to municipalities when it comes to sustainability and awareness-raising measures.
- Developing a budget based on communication and participation with targeted beneficiaries
- Removing barriers associated with subsidies: making subsidies clearer, integrating them and allocating them to meaningful and responsible activities. Making subsidies flexible according to the actual needs of the farmer and the condition of the landscape.
- Incorporating into legislation the lived experience of the people who manage land, local government representatives and local residents.
- Encouraging landowners' interest in how their land is managed (increase social responsibility).
- Launching information campaigns (let the public know about the farmers and their products).
- Improving and promoting communication amongst authorities.

MINISTRY OF EDUCATION

- Removing systemic barriers so that the public can be better educated and better trained.
- Raising the profile of agriculture through awareness and information campaigns.
- Including more practice in schools to foster a relationship with nature from an early age.
- Changing the definition of school curriculums and the teacher training system to better support teachers in imparting the relationship with the landscape to children.
- Supporting the creation and existence of more trade schools.
- Supporting school-based learning of labour and work on the school grounds in a way that gives them clear meaning.
- Encouraging schools to create programmes for children to care for and cultivate a relationship with greenery and the landscape.

STATE ADMINISTRATION ACROSS SECTORS

- Increasing and promoting accessibility and cooperation of officials towards farmers.
- Creating a barrier-free office, i.e. removing digital barriers, especially for older citizens.
- Delegating healthy responsibility to civil servants, who are often afraid to take it and end up not making any decisions.
- Creating experts and advisors out of officials; make them more accountable. If they are not competent, replace them; reduce the legislative burden placed on them as a result.
- Educating officials about the latest regulations and regulations. Ensuring that they can respond flexibly to legislative changes and amendments.

MEDIA

- Promoting awareness in society that the landscape and its management are not compatible with consumerism and comfortable city life.
- Supporting the elimination of stereotypes about conservationists.
- Informing the public about how costly work in agriculture is (eliminating negative stereotypes and labels attached to Czech agriculture).
- Raising the profile of agriculture through awareness and information campaigns.

REGIONS

- Launching information campaigns (let the public know about the farmers and their products).
- Providing financial support to municipalities for landscape revitalisation and making municipalities responsible for landscape care.
- Involving regions more - they have the ability to identify at-risk areas and then trigger mechanisms (financial and legislative) to support their restoration or conservation.
- Ensuring that regions initiate professional workshops for the public, farmers and municipalities.
- Supporting regions so that they can act as a mentor. Effectiveness of measures: securing experts and boosting public expertise.
- Increasing landscape permeability by building roads.
- Ensuring increased support for local farmers' products (supply chains support) with respect to capacities of the "what to sell" nature (cultivation support) and the "where and by whom" nature (supplying space for markets and buyers).

MUNICIPAL LEADERSHIP AND COUNCIL

- Using the municipal radio and newsletter as a tool to educate the public.
- Organising more events for children and adults with the purpose of getting them involved in or having them learn about landscape management.
- Ensuring that the municipality supports farmers in production (providing space and spreading the word that this or that farmer has something to offer).
- Ensuring that the municipality promotes food sovereignty through end-user outreach.
- Launching information campaigns (let the public know about the farmers and their products).
- Motivating individuals towards water retention actions that can be done by anyone.
- Increase the citizens' motivation to plant greenery.
- Increasing landscape permeability by building roads.
- Setting aside land for green measures.
- Abolishing land amelioration.
- Involving more experts in landscape management processes (from the smallest actions, e.g. tree pruning, to legislation).
- Encouraging landowners' interest in how their land is managed (increase social responsibility).
- Ensuring a smooth and speedy completion of complex land consolidation processes.
- Supporting land redistribution where there are multiple owners.
- Completing land-use plans. Systematically supporting spatial development.
- Supporting people's responsibility for land and the landscape.
- Addressing landowners' comments quickly.
- Ensuring continuity in municipal leadership.
- Producing educational and awareness workshops for landowners.
- Developing and completing complex land consolidation plans.
- Ensuring increased support for local farmers' products (supply chains support) with respect to capacities of the "what to sell" nature (cultivation support) and the "where and by whom" nature (supplying space for markets and buyers).

LOCAL GOVERNMENT

- Ensuring continuity in municipal leadership.
- Putting more emphasis on fostering people's relationship to the landscape.

MORE

- State Land Office: Making the Farmer's Portal simpler and more user-friendly, especially when it comes to senior citizens.
- Schools: Putting more emphasis on fostering people's relationship to the landscape.
- Church: Encouraging the Church to make better use of its local influence and the local influence of the clergy in caring for the landscape and in coordinating landscaping activities.
- Academy of Sciences: Using the Academy of Sciences as an authority in communicating information and addressing measures in the landscape.
- Union of Towns and Municipalities: Supporting agreement amongst municipalities and creating the space and capacity for it to happen.

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